

THEORETICAL BASIS OF FRACTOGRAPHIC STUDY OF THE WORKING CHAMBER OF A LINTER UNIT

Akramova Dilafruz Shukhrat kizi

PhD student, Namangan Engineering and Technological Institute

akramovad163@gmail.com ,

+998999774669

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13919980>

Annotation:

In this paper, a fractographic study of the working chamber of a linter unit and its key component, the agitator , was conducted . The purpose of the study was to analyze wear, cracking, and damage that occur during operation of the unit during the linting of cotton raw materials. The study showed that the main destruction mechanisms are abrasive wear and fatigue failure caused by friction between the chamber walls and the cotton raw materials, as well as dynamic loads associated with the rotation of the agitator . Based on the data obtained, recommendations are proposed to increase the service life of the equipment by improving materials and optimizing the design. The results of the study can be used to increase the efficiency of linter units and improve the quality of cotton processing.

Keywords: Linter unit, fractography , working chamber, stirrer , abrasive wear, fatigue failure, cotton raw material, friction, mechanical damage, design optimization.

Introduction

Fractographic research is aimed at studying the nature of destruction, wear and crack formation in equipment components, such as the working chambers of linter units, their stirrers and the surfaces of processed materials (in this case, cotton grains). The study of these processes helps to identify the causes of damage and suggest ways to increase the wear resistance and durability of equipment.

Main part

1. Study of the working chamber

The working chamber of the linter unit is the main part of the machine where the cotton raw material is processed, during which the linter fibers are separated from the cotton seeds. In this area, the unit is exposed to intense action of raw materials and equipment elements, such as a stirrer . Therefore, the study of the working chamber is aimed at analyzing its wear, mechanical

damage and optimizing operating conditions to increase the efficiency and durability of the unit.

Main characteristics of the working chamber:

Working chamber materials:

The chamber is usually made of wear-resistant steels, as it is subject to constant friction and exposure to abrasive particles of cotton raw materials. An important factor is the choice of material that can withstand high cyclic loads and abrasive effects of cotton seeds.

Abrasive wear:

One of the key factors affecting the service life of the working chamber is abrasive wear. Friction between the chamber walls and the cotton raw material leads to gradual destruction of the surface. The areas where seeds and fibers are mixed and moved are most susceptible to wear. Surfaces can be rough, with microcracks and worn areas.

Friction and mechanical effects:

An important aspect is the dynamic friction that occurs between the agitator blades and the chamber walls. This friction causes microcracks and fatigue damage on the chamber surface, which can cause further damage.

Microstructure of damage:

When conducting a fractographic study under a microscope, areas of local stress concentration are identified where damage accumulates. Microcracks often form in these areas, which increase over time, especially in corners or sharp transitions of the chamber, where uneven load distribution is created.

Improvement methods:

Use of wear-resistant coatings: Applying special coatings to the chamber surfaces that are resistant to abrasion can significantly extend the service life of the equipment.

Optimizing chamber geometry: Changing the shape and smoothing out sharp corners within the working chamber can reduce stress concentrations and the likelihood of fatigue failure.

Adjusting operating modes: Optimizing the rotation speed of the stirrer and other operating parameters of the machine can minimize friction and reduce mechanical loads on the working surfaces.

The analysis of the working chamber revealed that its main problem is abrasive wear and fatigue failure caused by friction and dynamic loads. The solution to these problems lies in the selection of more durable materials and coatings, as well as in the optimization of the design and operating conditions of the chamber.

2. Research of the stirrer

The agitator plays a key role in mixing and transporting cotton seeds in the working chamber. The main damages to the agitator are:

Wear of the blades due to constant contact with solid particles (cotton grains and fibers);

Mechanical cracks at the points where the blades are attached to the axis of rotation due to cyclic loads;

Damage from impacts against the walls of the working chamber, which leads to the appearance of cracks and deformations.

Fractographic analysis reveals characteristic microstructures of cracks on the agitator blades , which indicate fatigue failure. Wear traces in the form of microrelief, characteristic of abrasive wear, can also be detected.

3. Damage to the surface of cotton grains

The surfaces of cotton grains are also subject to mechanical stress during the ginning and linting process . The main types of damage include:

Mechanical abrasion of the seed coat, which can reduce the quality of the extracted lint ;

Damage from impacts of the stirrer blades , leading to partial destruction of the outer layers of the seeds.

Fractographic examination of cotton grains allows us to identify the mechanisms of shell destruction, which can help optimize the operating parameters of the units and reduce damage to the final product. Grain damage usually takes the form of impact cracks and abrasion marks.

Conclusion

Fractographic examination of the working chamber, agitator and damaged surface of cotton grains reveals key mechanisms of destruction and wear: abrasive wear, fatigue destruction and impact damage. Analysis of these processes allows developing recommendations for improving the materials, design and operating conditions of linter machines, which will increase their durability and efficiency.

Fractographic analysis of cotton grains revealed microscopic damage to the hulls caused by mechanical action and abrasive wear during the linting process . The most typical are microcracks and micropores, indicating the impact of friction and cyclic loads from the agitator and other machine elements.

List of references:

1. Abdullaev, R. A. Study of the parameters of gin saws in order to improve the quality and efficiency of ginning / R. A. Abdullaev. - Tashkent: Uzbek Institute of Textile and Light Industry, 2019. - 160 p.
2. Djalilov, H. M. Improvement of the technological process of linting at cotton ginning plants / H. M. Djalilov. - Tashkent: UzResearch Institute of Cotton Growing, 2020. - 140 p.
3. Niyazov, A. O. Optimization of linter machines operation based on the study of their working parts wear / A. O. Niyazov, I. T. Karimov // Bulletin of the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers. - 2018. - No. 3. - P. 35-42.
4. Rakhmanov, F. M. Analysis of wear resistance of working chambers of linter machines / F. M. Rakhmanov, Sh. I. Yuldashev // Cotton and textile technology. - 2017. - No. 2. - P. 45-53.
5. Alimov, B.K. Improvement of working bodies of linter equipment based on the study of the dynamics of the linting process / B.K. Alimov. - Tashkent: UzGTU , 2016. - 180 p